

Order of elemental analysis

*You can bring your samples (min 5 mg) to Sylvie (lab 07) on Mondays and Thursdays **between 9:30am and 11:00am***

Customer

Name: Marco Meyer	Date:05.11.16
Institute: Unibas inorganic chemistry	Tel: 0049 17627148199
Labor: BPR1096	Email: marco.meyer@stud.unibas.ch

Email supervisor: catherine.housecroft unibas.ch

Sample

Sample name: MEM012 [Cu(6-Cl-6'-methylbpy)(xantphos)][PF ₆]	
Aspect / texture: Powder	
Molecular formula: C ₅₀ H ₄₁ ClCuF ₆ N ₂ OP ₃	Molar mass: 991.80
Used solvent: Dichloromethane	
Structure:	

Sample details

Is the sample harmful? (skin, lungs, toxic)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample light sensitive?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample electrostatic?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample hygroscopic?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Do you want your sample back?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Additional informations:		

Elemental analysis

Sample name:

Single determination

Double determination

C <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	N <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Other elements: Cu, P, F, O, Cl		

Results

Analysis number:			
Sample name:			
Expected values:	C 60.55 %	H 4.17 %	N 2.82 %
Results:	C 58.63 % -%	H 4.11 % -%	N 2.74% -%
Other elements:			
Remarks:			

Date/Visa operator
 07.11.2018 / Michael Pfeffer